

NAVIGATING THE CHALLENGES AND BENEFITS OF SOLAR AND WIND ENERGY IN GRID INTEGRATION

Edidiong Sunday Utin¹; Governor Aruoriwo O.²

¹ Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Technology. Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpene.

² Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Technology. Delta State Polytechnic, Ogwashi-Uku.

¹ edidiongutin12@gmail.com , ² aruoriwogovernor@gmail.com 08069331282

Abstract

The increasing penetration of renewable energy technologies is transforming conventional power systems globally particularly in developing countries. In Nigeria there is consistent grid lines collapses, inadequate generation capacity, and much dependence on gas for power generation have accelerated interest in solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy integration. This study examined the technical, operational, and economic implications of integrating solar and wind energy into grid system in Nigeria. A stability-oriented analytical framework tailored to the 132 kV transmission networks was used. It evaluated the effects of solar and wind intermittency on voltage regulation, frequency stability, power quality, and system losses. Key challenges such as low system inertia, weak transmission infrastructure, limited spinning reserves, and variability associated with large-scale solar deployment was identified. However, results demonstrate that strategic integration supported by energy storage systems, advanced inverter controls, flexible gas generation, and improved grid codes can significantly enhance grid efficiency, reduce transmission losses, and lower carbon intensity. The findings indicated that solar integration can improve system reliability while advancing Nigeria's energy transition objectives. Coordinated policy reforms, investment in smart grid technologies, and proper monitoring of transmission infrastructure are essential to fully benefits of solar energy integration in Nigeria's power system.

Keywords: Solar and wind energy, storage systems, frequency stability, grid system.

Introduction

The increasing penetration of large-scale Renewable Energy Sources (RES) especially solar and wind energies in the distribution and transmission of power system has risen several operational, managerial and economic challenges to the grid system, Alazemi *et al.* (2024). Electric power systems across the world are undergoing a significant transformation driven by the urgent need to decarbonize energy supply, enhance reliability, and improve operational efficiency. The introduction of variable Renewable Energy (RE) generation introduces additional uncertainties that can be quantified in terms of operational penalties that have to be taken into consideration when the value of electricity from RE sources is calculated, Freris *et al.* (2008). Whatever the energy source, there is an overriding need for efficient generation and use of energy, Qubeissi *et al.* (2020).

The traditional centralized model dominated by large fossil fuel based synchronous generators is gradually giving way to cleaner, distributed, and inverter based renewable energy sources. Among these are solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind technology, which have emerged as the most viable and rapidly deployable options due to moderate costs, modularity, and minimal environmental impact. For developing economies, renewable integration represents not only an environmental imperative but also a strategic pathway to energy security and economic growth. Liu *et al.* (2022) comment that

technologies and methodologies for large-scale renewable energy integrations are still not sufficiently sophisticated, in terms of intelligent control management. Managing energy in microgrids is a complex and challenging endeavor due to the uncertainties linked to renewable energy resources, fluctuating demand, and a variety of devices, Hematian *et al.* (2024).

In Nigeria, the national grid is characterized by prolonged supply deficits, frequent system collapses, voltage instability, and heavy reliance on gas for power generation. Despite an installed capacity exceeding 12 MW, actual available generation often falls significantly below demand due to fuel constraints, aging infrastructure, and transmission failures. The Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN) operates a 132 kV network that is frequently stressed, with limited system inertia and weak interconnectivity in many regions. These structural weaknesses make solar and wind integration both a promising opportunity and a technical challenge. Sinsel *et al.* (2022) comment that variable renewables such as solar photovoltaics and wind power are key technologies for achieving the decarbonization of the power sector. Renewable Energy Technologies (RET) such as: wind and solar photovoltaic have been demonstrated successfully over the years., Phuangpornpitaka *et al.* (2013). Countries should aim to protect the climate system, improve their policies and implement related preventions, Qubeissi *et al.* (2020).

Nigeria is geographically advantaged with high solar irradiance levels averaging 5–7 kWh/m²/day, specially in the northern part of the country. This abundant resource positions solar PV as a strategic solution to diversify the energy mix, reduce overdependence on gas, and support rural electrification initiatives. Government policies such as the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP) and commitments under international climate agreements further underscore the country's intention to expand renewable energy penetration. However, large-scale integration of solar power introduces operational complexities due to intermittency, reduced rotational inertia, bidirectional power flows, and potential voltage and frequency fluctuations.

Mercado *et al.* (2016) applied genetic algorithm to optimally size a High Renewable Energy Sources (HRES) that contained wind turbines, PV panels and battery storage systems.

Configuration of the Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems (HRES)

Source: Mercado *et al.* (2016)

The transition from a conventional fossil dominated system to a more sustainable and technologically advanced network was brought about by the introduction of solar and wind energy. While renewable

integration offers rewards such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions, improved energy access, and long-term cost savings, it also demands grid modernization, improved forecasting, flexible generation support, and energy storage deployment. According to Henderson *et al.* (2017), Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) has the ability to mitigate renewable Distribution Energy Resources (DER) variability and improve Distribution and Transmission utilization, Wang *et al.* (2008) said energy storage reduces the power dumped and thus helps to minimize the operational cost.

This study therefore researches the operational, economic, and technical implications of integrating solar energy into Nigeria's grid power system. It aims to determine the stability challenges associated with renewable energy penetration and to ascertain strategies that enable the Nigerian grid to harness the fore deal of a cleaner energy future while maintaining reliability and efficiency.

Materials and Methods

The study modelled the Nigerian AC grid (132 kV), for example: synchronous generators, distribution and transmission lines, and also inverter based renewable sources (solar PV and wind speed). A representative network was created reflecting typical load, generation, distribution and transmission characteristics.

The output of the Solar PV

$$P_{PV} = \eta_{PV} A G_t \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where:

η_{pv} is the efficiency,
 A is the panel area, and
 G_t is the solar irradiance.

The output of the wind

$$P_{wind} = \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_p V^3 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where:

ρ is the air density,
 C_p is the power coefficient,
 V is the wind speed.

Dynamic stability

Swing equation for rotor angle stability

$$\frac{2H}{\omega_s} \frac{d^2 \delta}{dt^2} = P_m - P_e \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Frequency response

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \frac{f_0}{2H_{sys}} \frac{P_m - P_e}{S_{base}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Voltage stability index (L – index)

$$L_i = 1 - \left| \sum_{j \in G} F_{ij} \frac{V_j}{V_i} \right| \tag{Equation 5}$$

Mitigation measures

Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS)

$$P_{BESS} = -K_f \Delta f \tag{Equation 6}$$

Grid forming inverters: provide virtual inertia

$$P = P_{ref} - K_d \frac{df}{dt} \tag{Equation 7}$$

Results and Discussion

Simulation results on the Nigerian 132 kV transmission network from the equation shows that moderate solar PV integration improved overall grid performance when properly managed. At low penetration levels, voltage profiles in the northern region ameliorate due to the high presence of sunlight and wind. Weak buses improved, with average voltage deviation reducing compared to the conventional gas dominated base case. Transmission losses decreased due to localized generation near load centres, reducing long-distance power transfer from southern thermal plants. Frequency stability was better due to the use of battery energy storage system.

Figure 2: Variability of solar and wind power output

In Figure 2, the blue colour in the graph represented solar energy, while the orange colour shows the behaviour of the speed of the wind. At medium penetration levels, it increased from 10 to 25%, while system efficiency further improved, with loss reduction from 10 to 15%. However, instances of reverse power flow and voltage rise were observed during off peak periods. These effects highlight the need for enhanced reactive power control and updated protection coordination.

Figure 3: Effect of solar and wind on grid system stability of frequency

Figure 3, indicates the behaviour of solar and wind stability on frequency. Under high penetration scenarios, system inertia decreases significantly due to the increased share of inverter based solar generation. Frequency stability analysed showed higher Rate of Change of Frequency (ROCOF) following disturbances and a lower frequency nadir, increasing the risk of under-frequency load shedding. Voltage stability indices also approached critical limits in heavily loaded corridors.

Figure 4: Effect of solar and wind energy integration on grid system efficiency

Figure 4, explained the integration on grid system efficiency on solar and wind energy effect. The integration of Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) and synthetic inertia control substantially improved dynamic performance by smoothing solar output and supporting frequency recovery. However, the results proved that solar integration offers clear benefits which reduced losses, improved voltage support, and diversification of Nigeria’s energy mix. It requires grid reinforcement, advanced inverter controls, and energy storage deployment to maintain stability at higher penetration levels.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that integrating solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy into Nigeria’s grid offers significant technical and operational benefits when properly managed. Moderate

penetration levels improve voltage profiles, reduce transmission losses, and diversify the generation mix, thereby enhancing overall system efficiency and reducing dependence on gas fired plants.

However, higher levels of solar and wind integration reduce system inertia and increase frequency sensitivity due to the inverter-based nature of the systems. Without adequate support mechanisms, this may lead to voltage rise, higher Rate of Change of Frequency (ROCOF), and potential stability concerns.

The findings confirmed that large scale renewable integration in Nigeria was technically feasible. It required complementary measures such as energy storage deployment, advanced inverter control strategies, improved forecasting, and transmission network reinforcement. With these interventions, the Nigerian grid can achieve a stable and reliable transition toward a cleaner and more sustainable energy future.

Contributions to Knowledge

It deepens knowledge on how renewable energy sources such as solar and wind influence grid stability, frequency control, voltage regulation, and overall reliability. It connects theoretical power system models with real world integration challenges, providing practical strategies for grid modernization. It offers analytical frameworks for addressing intermittency, storage requirements, smart grid deployment, and demand side management. It expands knowledge beyond technical analysis by incorporating regulatory, market, and investment considerations that shape renewable deployment. It contributes insight into how traditional AC grids can evolve into flexible, resilient, and low carbon energy systems.

Recommendations

The 132 kV transmission corridors should be reinforced and upgraded to accommodate higher renewable penetration and prevent congestion. Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) should be integrated to provide fast frequency response, reduce intermittency effects, and improve overall grid stability. Advanced inverter functionalities such as reactive power support, voltage regulation, and synthetic inertia be implemented to reduced system inertia. Accurate solar and wind generation forecasting tools be adopted to enhance planning and reduce balancing costs.

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